

**EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF ANALYTICS
AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (EJAAI)**
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**Assessment of language as a communication barrier delay as construction services:
Case study from the Republic of Trinidad and Tobago**

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Abstract

The nature of the construction sector involves multiple players and is characterized by its complexity, fragmentation, and constant changes. To overcome these hurdles, effective communication is crucial. Previous research has highlighted that the industry struggles to maintain successful communication throughout project cycles, which often leads to failed projects. While previous studies have addressed inadequate communication in this industry, this particular study focuses on the reasons and outcomes of such problems. It conducts a thorough examination of earlier literature to determine what factors contribute to poor communication in construction projects.

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Introduction

Background of Study

Language is a significant issue within the construction industry as it creates communication barriers that can negatively affect project outcomes. The Oxford Dictionary defines language as the primary method of human communication, using words in a structured and conventional way through speech, writing or gesture. Communication barriers refer to anything that hinders the correct reception and acceptance of a message by its intended recipient. While communication is crucial for construction management, its importance is often limited to achieving specific objectives (Das & Mishra, 2020). Poor performance in the construction industry has been prevalent worldwide due to various factors such as ineffective communication caused by a lack of coordination within the work system. Researchers have become increasingly interested in studying communication-related issues in construction over time. Studies have shown that non-effective communication on construction sites results in problems such as cost overrun, time overrun, and project failure. Ineffective communication leads to unproductive outcomes and may be caused by misinterpretation or incomplete transmission of information or misunderstanding due to differing levels of education or unfamiliarity with the language used to convey the message. Poor communication can occur between different parties involved in a project (client, consultant, engineer or contractor) resulting in significant issues; however, internal miscommunication within firms can be remedied relatively easily compared to inter-party problems. Effective communication requires clear messaging tailored appropriately for its intended recipient's level of education and language comprehension abilities. Rahman (2019)

argues that effective communication is fundamental for success in any construction project as it encompasses core competencies necessary for successful completion.

Aim

The aim of this research is to assess language as a communication barrier delay in construction services and evaluate if it is a primary cause of the industry's poor performance.

Objectives

1. To use scholarship journals and articles to understand language as a communication barrier delay in the construction industry in Trinidad and Tobago compared to other countries.
2. To acquire data from the construction industry in Trinidad and Tobago using a questionnaire survey.
3. To compare the different ways language acts as a communication barrier delay in the industry.
4. To analyse whether this communication barrier is one of the main reasons for the setbacks in the industry.
5. To provide recommendations to reduce the impact of the language being a communication barrier delay in the industry.

Research Questions

1. How does language affect the communication barrier in the construction industry?
2. What are the different communication barriers in the industry?
3. How can this barrier affect the performance of the industry?
4. How can you overcome this communication barrier and what can you do in future to prevent any problems relating to this?

Scope of the study

The general purpose of this study is to assess language as a communication barrier delay in the construction industry and how it affects the outcome of the projects. This will be done by reviewing previous articles of similar content and comparing them. The prior literature will give a better understanding of how language acts as a communication barrier in the construction industry and what are the results due to it. Evaluating these barriers can help in developing ways to mitigate the negative impacts that it has on the industry. The study duration spans the current academic year (2022/2023), with design of the research methodology and literature analysis being done this semester, while the remainder of the research will begin next semester.

Assumptions

It can be assumed that:

- The respondents of the questionnaire answered genuinely and were not biased in their responses.
- The respondents possess the adequate knowledge about the field to self-report on elements being asked about.
- All sources, regardless of the date published is still applicable today.

Limitations

- There is limited number of local papers on the specific topic.
- Some articles were inaccessible due to certain restrictions.
- Depth of discussion is influenced by lack of prior experience with work such as this research project.
- Number of responses to questionnaire and their accuracy.

Literature Review

This literature review is geared toward presenting an interim perception and research into the subject of language as a communication barrier in the construction industry and how it causes delays in the industry. This addresses the objectives stated and how it has been dealt with throughout the years.

Throughout the years, researchers have conducted numerous investigations on poor communication in the construction industry, which has been identified as a major cause of project failure. As a result of its significance, there has been an increase in studies on this topic. Gamil (2023) highlighted poor communication in construction projects as an important issue that requires attention and developed a structural relationship model to clarify the causes and effects of poor communication. Language barriers have proven to be challenging for many countries, including Trinidad and Tobago and Malaysia (Ne'Matullah & Pek, 2021), posing risks for foreign workers and leading to time and manpower wastage. To address this issue, language modules were developed for foreign worker training. Misunderstanding the topic or words used can also create communication barriers between parties (Gamil, Yaser 2018). Moreover, using multiple vendors in projects can impact communication effectiveness due to differing service delivery methods requiring increased staff interaction (Pamidimukkala et al., 2023).

Some examples and practices of poor communication in the construction industry are lack of frequent communication within construction parties, the impact of material delivery deviations due to poor communication, and dispute among workers.

The issue of language barriers is widespread, affecting several industries, including construction services. According to research by Ne'Matullah and colleagues (2021), language barriers have resulted in significant productivity losses in Malaysia's construction sector. This highlights the importance of evaluating language as a communication barrier that delays progress and taking

steps to improve efficiency. The findings indicate that effective communication across industries requires mutual comprehensibility among all stakeholders involved; otherwise, misunderstandings can lead to errors or delays. Forbes Insights' survey (2011) also supports this conclusion by emphasizing how critical it is for organizations to address these issues upfront. As per the report's finding, 65% of executives reported experiencing difficulties due to language barriers between managers/executives and other workers leading to miscommunication and difficulty collaborating with each other being their most significant consequences Forbes Insights (2011). The inefficiencies ultimately resulting from such hindrances significantly contribute towards lower productivity levels throughout organizations.

In every language, there are four basic principle which are listening, reading, speaking and writing. These principles are all linked together and are key for the development of communication and language. Speaking is the action of conveying information and listening is taking notice of what someone says. The latter two principle, reading is the process of looking at written characters and getting meaning from them and writing is the act of forming visible and readable characters. Although it may sound simple, some of the workers in the industry may not be able read and understand complex contents and will therefore be a hinderance in the communication process. A study done by Ivanova (2019) showed we perceive the same words differently presuming that our partners perceive them the same way.

The construction industry is a major global sector that employs over 300 million people and contributes to 6.5% of annual growth (Johari, Sparsh, 2021). It is crucial to continuously recruit young and trained workers to avoid a shortage caused by the retirement of older workers. In many cases, countries face labour shortages due to high demand and may need to rely on migrant workers who move from other regions or countries in search of temporary employment. While these workers bring diverse skills and knowledge that can potentially speed up job completion, communication barriers between local and migrant workers can lead to significant

delays on construction sites. Studies conducted by Lin et al. (2017) and Wang et al. (2008) emphasize the importance of effective communication in promoting worker safety and productivity at job sites. Lack of proper training for migrant workers due to language barriers increases their likelihood of on-site injuries, making even simple tasks risky for them compared to local workers who are more experienced with complex jobs. As a result of this wage gaps between the migrant workers and local workers are created. Over the various studies looked at, the major cause of accidents on sites are due to poor worker communication and this results in a decrease in the performance of the worker. Effective communication is not a one-way process, it is a two-way process. Firstly, the task is given to the workers by the supervisor or engineer, and they must perform the given task. However, sometimes the task may not be stated clearly enough, or the choice of words used may cause the workers to misunderstand what the task was. If there was any misunderstanding through the process of communication due to the language used there will obviously be a setback in the project causing it to take more time and therefore more money. Secondly, there must be communication from the workers to the superior to allow for suggestions or correction in the task being done or even allow for the description of issues occurring on the site. If there is effective communication in which both parties understand each other fully, this will be the most effective and efficient project with the least number of on-site injuries. However, it is a fact that most construction workers are illiterate (Lin et al. 2017), and thus their poor educational backgrounds affect workplace communication. According to many of the articles referenced, it can be said that the low level of education of the workers result in the communication barrier. It is also seen that non-English speaking workers in an English-speaking country exaggerates the problem with communication on the site. In summary, these sources demonstrate how detrimental communication difficulties caused by linguistic discrepancies can be within any industry- particularly construction services where every aspect depends on proper coordination from all parties involved - highlighting why assessing languages should remain front-and-centre during improvement efforts aimed at generating more efficient production lines

so not only do stakeholders communicate better but ensure timely completion without sacrificing quality standards set forth earlier through careful consideration given towards potential points where obstacles may arise based upon previous experience learned along preceding projects.

In most cases, when the communication skills are poor within the workplace, workers tend to turn to unreliable methods of communication for example sign language. "Language barriers, discrimination issues, and miscommunication were significantly correlated with the work productivity of foreign workers" (Salleh et al., 2021). However, as mentioned, this is unreliable, and the message may not be properly understood. In one study, Dong et al. (2009) found miscommunication to be one of the primary causes of fall fatalities at construction sites. Past research has proposed numerous techniques to overcome such problems. for instance, one proposal is to create a small team of workers who communicate the identical language and assign a group leader who is aware of different languages to allow intergroup communication. Unfortunately, with these suggestions, comes its limitations and can be of a greater cost to the employer. Communication between workers is not the only issue in the industry. There needs to be effective communication between the employer and the supplier from which the required materials for a project are coming from. Many instances have occurred where the communication between these two said parties were misunderstood, and this have caused for the sending of the wrong materials or the delay in the sending of the materials. In a case study done by Xie, Wu, Luo and Hu (2010) showed the communication between multi-teams facing some difficulties as they most of the times don't understand each other or do not communicate properly. In some cases, there may be a dispute among any two of the said parties. When a dispute occurs, it can either be due to miscommunication or it can lead to the lack of communication between persons and frustration among workers. This lack of communication

causes the project to go haywire as accidents on site can occur, there will be ignorance of the tasks to be done and there will be wastage of time on the jobsite.

According to Bryan Cruz's (2022) article, "Techniques Against Language Barriers: A Company Case Study," language barriers in construction can lead to safety concerns for workers. Workers who do not speak English are unable to benefit from safety training or read operation manuals written only in English, and communicating with supervisors who don't speak Spanish can become difficult, leading to greater workplace injuries and deaths for Hispanics in construction. Cruz presents techniques currently being used by a construction company to combat language barriers, including having translators in safety meetings, conducting smaller meetings with groups in their native language, and providing English language training. These techniques can be used as a guide for other companies when developing inclusive safety plans. Hewage and Ruwanpura (2009) proposed a technological solution for the communication barrier in the construction industry using information technology such as a wireless network with a central server and data managers to create a network for quick and easy communication. However, the use of information technology is quite limited in the construction industry because although the world is evolving fast when it comes to technology the construction industry was not able to keep up with the evolution. Keeping with the same technological aspects to help with communication barriers, it is safe to say that today many messages are sent via social media platforms which would make the communication easier but also can still have some levels of misunderstanding when it comes to deciphering the message sent or received.

Effective communication has an immense positive impact on construction projects since misunderstandings caused by linguistic issues lead to delays or rework when tasks are carried out incorrectly or not at all due to miscommunications with instructions or materials required onsite. A thorough language program would provide workers and contractors with necessary skills required for clear communication resulting in reduced delays which ensure quality

workmanship throughout every phase of building projects. It's imperative to note that this type of training should go beyond basic grammar lessons; instead, specific terminologies used within the industry should be incorporated into their curriculum, so they know precisely what certain terms mean without requiring further clarification later – saving valuable time lost through poor comprehension caused by limited linguistic competence.

As it is seen, language is a communication barrier in the construction industry and it results in many problems such as cost overrun, injuries on site, missing of deadlines and lastly incompleteness of projects. Cost overrun is one of the most critical effects of the communication barrier as it indicates that the project has failed financially, and the client may get upset and this can lead to loss of credibility of the assigned company. Poor communication can also lead to high stress in workplace, wrong execution of activities which will result in time overrun, poor risk management and poor teamwork. In an assessment done by Rahman, Gamil (2019), showed that there were 41 causes of poor communication which resulted in 27 of effects some of which are mentioned above.

For further studies, it should go in some more detail as to how much times miscommunication occurs on a job site and relate it to how it affects the outcome of the project. Also, some more solutions should be found to mitigate the problem of language being a communication barrier in the construction industry. although most solutions have their limitations, more can be done to ensure that the number of limitations is reduced to a significantly small amount.

Methodology

Proposed Data Collection

Figure 1: Flow Chart Diagram showing the methodology used.

The flow chart diagram above in Figure 1 shows the methodology for this research project.

Firstly, research was done to find literary pieces related to the topic of language as a communication barrier delay in the construction industry. Qualitative research was carried out which involved the collection and analysis of the non-numerical data found in the previous articles and research papers. In doing this, a large amount of information was found to create the literature review. For quantitative research, a questionnaire was created and given out to the various stakeholders (engineers, contractors, labourers) to gain greater knowledge of the topic from a different perspective and aid in the answering of the research questions. The data collected will be used to create comparison using tables on how language is a communication barrier.

Data Collection

To gather information and verify the communication challenges that were identified in a literature review, a method involving a questionnaire survey was used. This survey will take the form of a cross-sectional study where data is collected from various segments of the population at one specific point in time. The chosen group to participate in this research were construction companies that have expressed interest and were willing to

provide their input. This approach allowed for a comprehensive examination of communication barriers within the context of construction companies, which can inform future strategies for improving communication within the industry. When filling out the questionnaire, you were required to assign a score to each answer based on two factors: the Probability Scale and Severity Index. These two scales will range from 1-5, with 1 indicating the worst possible outcome and 5 indicating the best. However, it is important to keep in mind that the specific terms assigned to each number on these scales will vary depending on the question being asked. The questionnaire created was distributed to 50 persons in the industry and the data collected was used for the analysis.

Analytical Tools

For the analysis of the data both SPSS and Microsoft Excel were used.

SPSS:

The widely used Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) is renowned for its exceptional performance in accurately processing and analysing survey data, making it a popular choice among various groups such as market researchers, survey companies, education researchers, and government entities. Currently owned by IBM, SPSS is claimed to be user-friendly, scalable and versatile that can be utilized with ease by users of all proficiency levels. With its numerous features, the intended outcomes of using SPSS software are to attain frequency distribution results such as mean scores and standard deviations and rankings based on acquired data.

Microsoft Excel:

Once the data has been meticulously processed through the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), it will be time to focus on presenting it in an engaging and visually appealing way. This is where Microsoft Excel comes into play. Microsoft Excel is a versatile tool that can be used to arrange and exhibit all the pertinent information garnered from the research. By utilising its wide array of features, such as tables, charts, graphs, and diagrams, one can effortlessly represent and showcase even complex statistical findings in an easy-to-comprehend manner. With its user-friendly interface, it is possible to create intricate visualisations with just a few clicks. The bar graphs are very useful when comparing variables, while pie charts give a clear indication of how various components contribute to a whole. Additionally, line graphs facilitate tracking changes over time quite effectively. All these figures created via Microsoft Excel make interpreting data much more straightforward for researchers or any relevant stakeholders who may not have an advanced understanding of statistics or data science fields.

Analysis of Data

After collecting the questionnaires with the results, it was organized in an excel file and from that it was inserted in SPSS to do some further analysis and the following tables and figures were generated.

Gender		
	N	%
F	22	44.0%
M	28	56.0%

Table 1 showing the number of males and females.

Figure 1 Bar chart showing males and females.

The following tables and charts were created using the Risk Significance Index which is Probability x Severity, and the probability and severity were answered in the questionnaire. For the Risk Significance Index the lower the value the less effective and the greater the value, the greater the concern. we calculate our risk level, from 1 (Very Low Risk) to 25 (Very High Risk) using the 5x5 risk matrix.

Table 2 Showing the Risk Significance Index and its meaning.

Risk Significance Index(Language as a comm barrier)

	N	%
1	1	2.0%
6	3	6.0%
9	8	16.0%
12	6	12.0%
16	14	28.0%
20	12	24.0%
25	6	12.0%

Table 3 showing risk significance index for Language as a communication barrier.

Figure 2 showing the risk significance index for the Section B Q1 in questionnaire: do language act as a communication barrier.

Risk Significance Index (Comm Barries effects)

	N	%
1	1	2.0%
4	1	2.0%
6	1	2.0%
9	8	16.0%
12	6	12.0%
16	19	38.0%
20	8	16.0%
25	6	12.0%

Table 4 risk significance index for effects of communication barrier.(Section B Q2 in questionnaire)

Figure 3 showing risk significance index for effects of communication barrier. (Section B Q2 in questionnaire)

The upcoming analysis is for what can be classified as communication barriers in the construction industry.

**Risk Significance Index
(Misunderstanding of
migrant workers)**

	N	%
1	2	4.0%
2	2	4.0%
4	2	4.0%
6	3	6.0%
9	11	22.0%
12	4	8.0%
16	12	24.0%
20	12	24.0%
25	2	4.0%

Table 5 risk significance index for misunderstanding of migrant workers. (Section B Q4 in questionnaire)

Figure 4 showing risk significance index for misunderstanding of migrant workers. (Section B Q4 in questionnaire)

**Risk Significance Index
(Unclear messages from
the superior)**

	N	%
1	2	4.0%
2	5	10.0%
3	8	16.0%
4	1	2.0%
6	6	12.0%
8	1	2.0%
9	3	6.0%
12	7	14.0%
16	8	16.0%
20	7	14.0%
25	2	4.0%

Table 6 Risk Significance index for unclear messages from superior. (Section B Q3 in questionnaire)

Figure 5 Risk Significance index for unclear messages from superior. (Section B Q3 in questionnaire)

**Risk Significance Index
(Low level education)**

	N	%
1	2	4.0%
2	5	10.0%
3	4	8.0%
4	1	2.0%
6	8	16.0%
8	1	2.0%
9	4	8.0%
12	10	20.0%
16	9	18.0%
20	4	8.0%
25	2	4.0%

Table 7 risk significance index for low level education. (Section B Q5 in questionnaire)

Figure 6 risk significance index for low level education.(Section B Q5 in questionnaire)

**Risk Significance Index
(Overload of information)**

	N	%
1	3	6.0%
2	1	2.0%
4	2	4.0%
6	7	14.0%
9	10	20.0%
12	9	18.0%
16	11	22.0%
20	5	10.0%
25	2	4.0%

Table 8 Risk Significance Index for Overload of Information (Section B Q6 in questionnaire)

Figure 7 Risk Significance Index for Overload of Information (Section B Q6 in questionnaire)

The upcoming analysis is for what can be classified as effects of communication barriers in the construction industry.

Risk Significance Index (Dispute)

	N	%
1	2	4.0%
2	5	10.0%
3	8	16.0%
4	1	2.0%
6	6	12.0%
8	1	2.0%
9	3	6.0%
12	7	14.0%
16	8	16.0%
20	7	14.0%
25	2	4.0%

Table 9 Risk Significance Index for Dispute among any parties (Section B Q9 in questionnaire)

Risk Significance Index(Dispute)

Figure 8 Risk Significance Index for Dispute among any parties (Section B Q9 in questionnaire)

**Risk Significance Index
(Time Overrun)**

	N	%
6	5	10.0%
9	8	16.0%
12	9	18.0%
16	14	28.0%
20	10	20.0%
25	4	8.0%

Table 10 Risk Significance Index for Time Overrun (Section B Q7 in questionnaire)

Figure 9 Risk Significance Index for Time Overrun (Section B Q7 in questionnaire)

**Risk Significance Index
(Cost Overrun)**

	N	%
6	4	8.0%
9	7	14.0%
12	8	16.0%
15	1	2.0%
16	17	34.0%
20	10	20.0%
25	3	6.0%

Table 11 Risk Significance Index for Cost Overrun (Section B Q8 in questionnaire)

Figure 10 Risk Significance Index for Cost Overrun (Section B Q8 in questionnaire)

**Risk Significance Index
(Project Failure)**

	N	%
1	2	4.0%
2	2	4.0%
4	2	4.0%
6	3	6.0%
9	11	22.0%
12	4	8.0%
16	12	24.0%
20	12	24.0%
25	2	4.0%

Table 12 Risk Significance Index for Project Failure (Section B Q10 in questionnaire)

Figure 11 Risk Significance Index for Project Failure (Section B Q10 in questionnaire)

The upcoming analysis is for what can be classified as possible solutions for communication barriers in the construction industry.

**Risk Significance Index
(Language Training)**

	N	%
1	2	4.0%
2	6	12.0%
3	1	2.0%
4	2	4.0%
6	10	20.0%
9	6	12.0%
12	9	18.0%
16	12	24.0%
20	1	2.0%
25	1	2.0%

Table 13 Risk Significance Index for Language Training (Section B Q13 in questionnaire)

Figure 12 Risk Significance Index for Language Training (Section B Q13 in questionnaire)

**Risk Significance Index
(Translator)**

	N	%
6	4	8.0%
9	7	14.0%
12	8	16.0%
15	1	2.0%
16	17	34.0%
20	10	20.0%
25	3	6.0%

Table 14 Risk Significance Index for Language Translator ((Section B Q12 in questionnaire)

Figure 13 Risk Significance Index for Language Translator ((Section B Q12 in questionnaire)

Risk Significance Index (Tech)

	N	%
1	2	4.0%
2	2	4.0%
4	2	4.0%
6	3	6.0%
9	11	22.0%
12	4	8.0%
16	12	24.0%
20	12	24.0%
25	2	4.0%

Table 15 Risk Significance Index for Language Technological solution (Section B Q11 in questionnaire)

Figure 14 Risk Significance Index for Language Technological solution (Section B Q11 in questionnaire)

		Statistics												
		Risk Significance Index (Language as a comm barrier)	Risk Significance Index(Comm Barries effects)	Risk Significance Index(Unclear messages from the superior)	Risk Significance Index (Misunderstanding of migrant workers)	Risk Significance Index(Low level education)	Risk Significance Index (Language Training)	Risk Significance Index (Translator)	Risk Significance Index(Tech)	Risk Significance Index(Project Failure)	Risk Significance Index(Overload of information)	Risk Significance Index(Dispute)	Risk Significance Index(Time Overrun)	Risk Significance Index(Cost Overrun)
N	Valid	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		15.54	15.38	10.26	13.22	10.28	9.68	14.90	13.22	13.22	11.58	10.26	14.68	14.90
Std. Deviation		5.856	5.628	7.108	6.390	6.484	5.751	4.979	6.390	6.390	5.990	7.108	5.408	4.979

Table 16 showing all the mean risk significance index for comparison.

Figure 15 Bar Chart showing the different communication barriers and their mean Risk significance index.

Figure 16 Bar Chart showing the different communication barriers effects and their mean Risk significance index.

Figure 17 Bar Chart showing the different solutions to communication barriers and their mean Risk significance index.

Correlations

		Risk Significance Index (Language as a comm barrier)	Risk Significance Index(Comm Barries effects)
Risk Significance Index (Language as a comm barrier)	Pearson Correlation	1	.897**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001
	N	50	50
Risk Significance Index (Comm Barries effects)	Pearson Correlation	.897**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	
	N	50	50

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 17 showing Correlation values calculated from SPSS.

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0						
	t	df	Significance		Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
			One-Sided p	Two-Sided p		Lower	Upper
Risk Significance Index (Language as a comm barrier)	18.764	49	<.001	<.001	15.540	13.88	17.20

Table 18 Showing one sample test calculated from SPSS.

Discussion

The construction services industry is one of the most significant sectors in any economy. However, it faces numerous challenges that can impede its efficiency and productivity. One of these obstacles is language barriers that delay communication between contractors, supervisors, and laborers from different linguistic backgrounds. This thesis statement highlights the critical issue of assessing language as a communication barrier delay to improve efficiency and productivity in the construction services industry. One interpretation of this statement is that language barriers inhibit effective communication among workers from diverse cultural backgrounds. Such impediments could lead to delays in executing tasks, misinterpretations of instructions or plans leading to errors or rework, poor coordination among team members resulting in low morale and lost time. Additionally, if not addressed promptly, these issues could cause project delays and cost overruns. Another implication worth noting is that addressing such challenges requires an understanding of what causes them in the first place. This may involve analysing factors such as workforce diversity levels (including demographics), training programs for staff on cross-cultural communication skills as well as identifying technologies designed specifically for improving communications across multiple languages. When working with others who don't share your native tongue or have limited language skills, misunderstandings can lead to errors and delays which pose challenges for project management as well as quality control processes and safety procedures. To address these issues more comprehensively means recognizing the extent of linguistic barriers across different contexts within construction projects before creating specific intervention measures aimed at addressing communication breakdowns due to differing languages.

From the questionnaire, the raw data collected were placed in an excel file for organization which will be seen in the appendix. The questionnaire provided values for probability and severity and from that the risk significance index was calculated by multiplying the probability by the severity. The value calculated gave an idea of how relevant the given question was to the

topic. For example, as you can see in Figure 2, the mean risk significance index was 15.54. this value was the values for the question of if it was thought that language acts as a communication barrier and this value suggest that many persons agreed to a higher extent. If the mean value was under 10 it would've suggested that many people did not think that way. According to Gamil (2023), from the research findings it can be validated that language is indeed a communication barrier in the construction industry. This was validated with the questionnaire findings also. Figure 3 showcased the effects of language as a communication barrier and the mean was found to be 15.38. According to research by Ne'Matullah and colleagues (2021), they also agreed with communication barriers having a negative effect on the construction industry and this was validated with the research findings. In addition to this, Ne'Matullah and colleagues (2021) also mentioned that the misunderstanding of migrant workers is one of the most common communication barriers and as you can see from the analysis of the data gathered, that has the highest mean Risk Significance Index therefore is the most likely. According to (Pamidimukkala et al., 2023), the increased interactions between parties resulted in a rise in problems and from the analysis, unclear messages from the superior had the lowest mean significance index but it was still at a value that would be likely. From Salleh et al., 2021, it is mentioned that language barriers are one of the main causes of setbacks in the industry which implies time overrun. From the analysis, it is seen that cost overrun and time overrun had very close mean risk significance index both over 14 which indicates it is highly likely and validates Salleh's statements. With regards to the solutions for language as a communication barrier in the construction industry, Cruz, Bryan (2022) , proposed one of his main solutions being translators in meetings and from the analysis above, it is seen that translator had the highest mean risk significance index and therefore was the most popular option.

Conclusion

To conclude, evaluating the role of language as a communication obstacle in the construction sector is a crucial subject that requires further attention and investigation. From our review of relevant literature, it is undeniable that linguistic barriers have significant ramifications for safety, productivity, and project success overall. It is therefore imperative for stakeholders to acknowledge the importance of effective communication in delivering successful projects.

Summing up what we have learned so far from this analysis of previous research; there are several factors contributing to language barriers such as cultural divergence, lack of translation services or proficiency with other languages. Moreover, methods were identified to tackle these difficulties through worker training programs and offering multilingual resources on job sites. Finally, yet most importantly; companies operating under construction should embrace diversity by creating an inclusive environment where all employees feel appreciated regardless of their country's heritage or dialect spoken. This will create open lines of communication which are necessary for efficient teamwork leading to quality outputs in each project. In conclusion, addressing language barriers should be at high priority not only within organizations but across various industries worldwide. Handling these problems effectively would result in greater workforce diversity ultimately leading to better decision-making processes and increased creativity opportunities. In summary, implementing language assessments can improve communication among workers from different linguistic backgrounds while promoting diversity and inclusivity within the industry. It is time for construction service providers to recognize this need and act towards ensuring effective communication through language fluency.

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Appendix

Appendix I: Gantt Chart

Appendix II: Plagiarism Form

Plagiarism Declaration

THE UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST INDIES

**The Office of the Board for Undergraduate
Studies**

**INDIVIDUAL PLAGIARISM
DECLARATION**

STUDENT ID: 816022953

COURSE TITLE: Special Investigative Project

COURSE CODE: CVNG 3015/3021

TITLE OF ASSIGNMENT:

Assessment of language as a communication barrier delay as construction services: Case study from the Republic of Trinidad and Tobago

This declaration is being made in accordance with the **University Regulations on Plagiarism (First Degrees, Diplomas and Certificates)** and must be attached to all work, submitted by a student to be assessed in partial or complete fulfilment of the course requirement(s), other than work submitted in an invigilated examination.

STATEMENT

1. I have read the Plagiarism Regulations as set out in the Faculty or Open Campus Student Handbook and on university websites related to the submission of coursework for assessment.
2. I declare that I understand that plagiarism is a serious academic offence for which the University may impose severe penalties.
3. I declare that the submitted work indicated above is my own work, except where duly acknowledged and referenced and does not contain any plagiarized material.
4. I also declare that this work has not been previously submitted for credit either in its entirety or in part within the UWI or elsewhere. Where work was previously submitted, permission has been granted by my Supervisor/Lecturer/Instructor as reflected by the attached Accountability Statement.
5. I understand that I may be required to submit the work in electronic form and accept that the University may subject the work to a computer-based similarity detection service.

NAME: Amisha Patandeen

SIGNATURE:

DATE: 17/04/2023

Appendix III: Notes on the important Literature Survey

Objective	Author	Title	Source	Method	Findings	Critique
1,3 and 4	Yaser Gamil, Ismail Abdul Rahman	Identification of Causes and Effects of Poor Communication in Construction Industry: A Theoretical Review	DOAJ Directory of Open Access Journals - Not for CDI Discovery	A research paper that focused on the causes and effects of poor communication in the construction industry	here many causes of poor communication were identified followed by the effects	the effects were not in much detail
3	Johari, Sparsh; Jha, Kumar Neeraj	Exploring the Relationship between Construction Workers' Communication	EBSCOhost EJS; ASCE Journals	a research paper comparing the communication skill to the performance of the workers	this was a very detailed paper where it showed how the productivity is affected by the various aspects of communication	none

		Skills and Their Productivity				
1,2	Xie, Charlene; Wu, Dash; Luo, Jianwen; Hu, Xiaoling; Segerstedt, Anders	A case study of multi-team communications in construction design under supply chain partnering	Web of Science - Social Sciences Citation Index - 2010; Emerald eJournals Premier; ABI/INFORM Global; ProQuest Central	a case study	this focused on teamwork and how important it is for communication within a team	none
1,3,4	Gamil, Yaser; Abd Rahman, Ismail	Studying the relationship between causes and effects of poor communication in construction projects using PLS-SEM approach	Emerald eJournals Premier; ABI/INFORM Global; ProQuest Central	research journal	this like the Yaser, Rahaman paper also focused on many different causes and effect of miscommunication in the construction industry	none

1,3,4	Danchevskaya, Oksana; Pustovgar, A.; Adamtsevich, A.; Volkov, A.	Potential risks in cross-cultural communication in construction	DOAJ Directory of Open Access Journals - Not for CDI Discovery; ProQuest Central	research paper	this paper focused more on cross cultural communication, so it gave finding on how communication is affected when it comes to migrant workers	none
5	Zhong, Ying ; Pheng Low, Sui	Managing crisis response communication in construction projects - from a complexity perspective	Web of Science - Social Sciences Citation Index - 2009; Emerald eJournals Premier; ABI/INFORM Global; ProQuest Central	research paper	this focused on trying to manage some of the communication issues in the construction industry	the solution had way too many limitations so most likely might not be too effective
1,3,4	Demchenko, V ;	Communication Barriers of a	Alma/SFX Local Collection; ProQuest Central	article	this article featured the different type of	none

	Khoroshevskay a, J ; Krukov, K	Construction Company's Network Management			communication barriers which showcased that language is a key contribution to the miscommunication	
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Appendix IV: Student Logbook

Summary record of major progress meetings with supervisors		Student name: Amisha Patandeen	Working title of dissertation/research project: Assessment of language as a communication barrier delay as construction services: Case study from the Republic of Trinidad and Tobago	
Meeting date & supervisors present	Progress since last meeting	Agreed programme of work and target dates	Other issues, e.g., facilities, supervision, training needs, etc.	Date of next meeting
26/09/22 Mr. Aaron Chadee	First meeting to discuss topic and a sample paper was given.			To be determined
07/11/22 Mr. Aaron Chadee	WhatsApp chat to discuss the final parts of the report			
17/02/23 Mr. Aaron Chadee	Meeting to discuss what needed to be changed and done to move forward with the analysis section			

Appendix V: Sample Questionnaire

Questionnaire

This questionnaire is a part of a research project that is being done to assess language as a communication barrier in the construction industry. This information provided is completely anonymous and would be used to do some analysis for the research project.

Section 1: Demographics

1. Gender

Male

Female

2. What sector do you work in?

Private

Public

3. Role at your place of work:

Engineer

Contractor

Employer

Consultant

Construction Worker

Other

4. Please indicate the number of employees in your organization:

< 20

21 – 50

51 – 100

100

5. Please indicate your personal experience in the following fields by ticking the appropriate box(years)

	0-5 years	6-10 years	11-15 years	16-20 years	>20 years	N/A
Engineering						
Contracting						
Project Management						
Architecture						
Consultancy						
Other						

In your opinion, what is the level of risk (Risk significance index = Probability x Severity) for what would be described as poor communication in the workplace:

	Probability					Severity				
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Extremely low	Low	Moderate	High	Extremely high
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
3. Unclear messages from the superior										
4. Misunderstanding of migrant workers										
5. Low level education										
6. Overload of information										

In your opinion, what is the level of risk (Risk significance index = Probability x Severity) for what would be described as effects of poor communication in the workplace:

	Probability					Severity				
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Extremely low	Low	Moderate	High	Extremely high
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
7. Cost overrun										
8. Time overrun										

ID	Gender	Unclear messages from the superior		Risk Significance Index(Unclear messages from the superior)	Misunderstanding of migrant workers		Risk Significance Index(Misunderstanding of migrant workers)	Low level education		Risk Significance Index(Low level education)	Overload of information		Risk Significance Index(Overload of information)	Cost Overrun		Risk Significance Index(Cost Overrun)
		Probability	Severity		Probability	Severity		Probability	Severity		Probability	Severity		Probability	Severity	
1	M	3	1	3	5	4	20	4	3	12	4	3	12	4	4	16
2	M	3	1	3	5	4	20	3	1	3	5	4	20	4	3	12
3	F	4	3	12	4	4	16	4	3	4	4	4	16	4	4	16
4	M	3	2	6	4	4	16	3	2	6	4	3	12	4	4	16
5	F	2	1	2	5	4	20	2	1	2	5	4	20	5	4	20
6	M	3	1	3	4	4	16	3	1	3	4	4	16	5	4	20
7	M	3	2	6	4	4	16	3	2	6	3	3	9	5	5	25
8	M	4	4	16	5	5	25	3	3	9	5	5	25	5	3	15
9	M	4	3	12	4	5	20	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	3	12
10	F	5	4	20	3	3	9	5	4	20	3	3	9	5	4	20
11	F	4	4	16	4	3	12	4	4	16	4	3	12	4	4	16
12	F	4	3	12	4	3	12	4	3	12	4	3	12	3	3	9
13	M	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	2	6
14	F	4	3	12	5	4	20	4	3	12	4	4	16	4	4	16
15	M	4	4	16	4	4	16	3	4	12	4	4	16	4	4	16
16	F	5	5	25	2	2	4	4	5	20	2	2	4	5	4	20
17	M	4	3	12	4	5	20	4	3	12	4	3	12	3	3	9
18	M	4	2	8	1	1	1	4	2	8	1	1	1	4	3	12
19	F	3	1	3	3	3	9	3	2	6	3	3	9	5	4	20
20	F	3	1	3	3	3	9	3	1	3	3	2	6	4	3	12
21	F	4	4	16	3	3	9	4	3	12	3	3	9	3	2	6
22	M	3	2	6	5	4	20	3	2	6	5	4	20	4	4	16
23	M	5	4	20	4	4	16	5	4	20	4	4	16	4	4	16
24	M	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	3	2	6	4	4	16
25	M	3	1	3	4	4	16	3	2	6	4	4	16	3	3	9
26	M	3	1	3	5	4	20	4	4	16	4	3	12	4	3	12
27	M	4	3	12	3	2	6	4	3	12	3	2	6	3	2	6
28	F	1	1	1	3	3	9	1	1	1	3	3	9	4	4	16
29	F	4	4	16	3	2	6	4	4	16	3	2	6	5	5	25
30	M	4	5	20	2	2	4	3	3	9	2	2	4	4	4	16
31	F	3	2	6	5	4	20	3	2	6	4	4	16	4	3	12
32	F	3	3	9	1	2	2	3	3	9	1	1	1	4	4	16
33	F	2	1	2	4	3	12	2	1	2	4	3	12	5	4	20
34	M	2	2	4	4	3	12	2	2	4	4	3	12	5	4	20
35	M	1	1	1	4	4	16	1	1	1	4	4	16	4	4	16
36	M	4	4	16	3	2	6	4	5	20	3	2	6	3	3	9
37	F	4	5	20	3	3	9	4	4	16	3	3	9	3	3	9
38	F	5	5	25	3	3	9	5	5	25	3	3	9	4	3	12
39	M	5	4	20	5	5	25	4	4	16	5	5	25	5	4	20
40	M	3	2	6	5	4	20	3	2	6	5	4	20	4	4	16
41	F	1	2	2	4	4	16	1	2	2	4	3	12	4	4	16
42	F	2	1	2	4	5	20	2	1	2	3	2	6	4	3	12
43	M	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	5	5	25
44	F	5	4	20	1	1	1	5	5	25	1	1	1	5	4	20
45	M	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	3	2	6
46	M	4	5	20	3	3	9	4	4	16	3	3	9	3	3	9
47	M	3	2	6	3	3	9	3	2	6	3	2	6	4	4	16
48	F	3	3	9	4	4	16	4	3	12	4	4	16	5	4	20
49	F	3	1	3	5	4	20	3	1	3	5	4	20	3	3	9
50	M	4	3	12	3	3	9	4	3	12	3	3	9	4	4	16

Table 19 showing raw data organized in excel.

Time Overrun		Risk Significance Index(Time Overrun)		Dispute in the job place (between any parties)		Risk Significance Index(Dispute)		Project Failure		Risk Significance Index(Project Failure)		Technological solution such as network to allow easy communication		Risk Significance Index(Tech)		Translator for non-English speaking workers		Risk Significance Index(Translator)		Extensive language training program		Risk Significance Index(Language Training)		Do you think that language is a communication barrier in the construction industry?		Risk Significance Index(Language as a comm barrier)		Does communication barrier cause hinderances in projects?		Risk Significance Index(Comm Barries effects)	
Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity
4	4	16	3	1	3	5	4	20	5	4	20	4	4	16	3	3	9	4	4	16	3	3	9	4	4	16	3	4	16	3	4
4	3	12	3	1	3	5	4	20	5	4	20	4	3	12	3	1	3	4	3	12	3	1	3	4	3	12	4	4	12	4	4
4	4	16	4	3	12	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	3	12	4	4	16	4	3	12	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4
4	3	12	3	2	6	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	3	2	6	3	4	16	3	2	6	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3
5	4	20	2	1	2	5	4	20	5	4	20	5	4	20	2	2	4	3	2	20	2	2	4	3	2	6	4	4	20	5	4
5	4	20	3	1	3	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	5	4	20	3	2	20	3	2	6	5	4	20	5	4	20	5	4
4	4	16	3	2	6	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	5	5	25	3	2	25	3	2	6	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4
4	3	12	4	4	16	5	5	25	5	5	25	5	3	15	3	3	9	5	5	15	3	3	9	5	5	25	5	5	25	5	5
4	3	12	4	3	12	4	5	20	4	5	20	4	3	12	4	4	16	4	4	12	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4
5	5	25	5	4	20	3	3	9	3	3	9	5	4	20	4	4	16	4	4	20	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4
4	4	16	4	4	16	4	3	12	4	3	12	4	3	12	4	4	16	4	4	12	4	4	16	4	4	20	4	4	16	4	4
3	3	9	4	3	12	4	3	12	4	3	12	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3	9	5	5	25	5	5	25	5	5
3	2	6	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3	6	3	2	9	3	2	6	3	2	9	5	4	20	5	4	20	5	4
4	4	16	4	3	12	5	4	20	5	4	20	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	20	4	4	16	4	4	12	3	3	9	3	3
4	3	12	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	3	4	12	4	4	16	3	4	12	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4
5	4	20	5	5	25	2	2	4	2	2	4	2	2	4	5	4	20	4	5	20	4	5	20	5	4	20	5	5	25	5	5
3	3	9	4	3	12	4	5	20	4	5	20	4	3	9	4	3	9	4	3	9	4	3	12	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3
4	4	16	4	2	8	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	3	12	3	2	6	2	3	12	3	2	6	2	3	6	2	2	4	2	4
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4	4	16	4	3	12	3	3	9	3	3	9	4	4	16	4	3	12	3	3	16	4	3	12	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3

Table 20 continued raw data organized in exce

Appendix VI: Originality Report

816022953			
ORIGINALITY REPORT			
6%	5%	2%	2%
SIMILARITY INDEX	INTERNET SOURCES	PUBLICATIONS	STUDENT PAPERS
PRIMARY SOURCES			
1	Sparsh Johari, Kumar Neeraj Jha. "Exploring the Relationship between Construction Workers' Communication Skills and Their Productivity", Journal of Management in Engineering, 2021 Publication	1%	
2	Submitted to University of Greenwich Student Paper	1%	
3	www.elliston.sa.gov.au Internet Source	1%	
4	repository.up.ac.za Internet Source	1%	
5	ltu.diva-portal.org Internet Source	<1%	
6	www.provenant.net Internet Source	<1%	
7	docu.tips Internet Source	<1%	
8	Submitted to University of Colorado, Denver Student Paper		

		<1 %
9	core.ac.uk Internet Source	<1 %
10	assets.researchsquare.com Internet Source	<1 %
11	www.researchgate.net Internet Source	<1 %
12	apo.org.au Internet Source	<1 %
13	pdfs.semanticscholar.org Internet Source	<1 %
14	ndl.ethernet.edu.et Internet Source	<1 %
15	Luz S. Marín, Cora Roelofs. "Promoting Construction Supervisors' Safety-Efficacy to Improve Safety Climate: Training Intervention Trial", <i>Journal of Construction Engineering and Management</i> , 2017 Publication	<1 %
16	etd.cput.ac.za Internet Source	<1 %
17	dspace.knust.edu.gh Internet Source	<1 %

open.library.ubc.ca

18	Internet Source	<1 %
19	www.koreascience.or.kr Internet Source	<1 %
20	Zein Wali, Khaled Elsayed, Abdel-karim Hassan. "Static RWA in All-Optical Network under Multifiber, Multiple Requests Assumption", 2006 International Conference on Computer Engineering and Systems, 2006 Publication	<1 %
21	ciobwcs.com Internet Source	<1 %
22	erepository.uonbi.ac.ke Internet Source	<1 %
23	nsuworks.nova.edu Internet Source	<1 %
24	www.ijsrp.org Internet Source	<1 %
25	Submitted to Northcentral Student Paper	<1 %

Exclude quotes OnExclude matches OffExclude bibliography On

Abstract

The nature of the construction sector involves multiple players and is characterized by its complexity, fragmentation, and constant changes. To overcome these hurdles, effective communication is crucial. Previous research has highlighted that the industry struggles to maintain successful communication throughout project cycles, which often leads to failed projects. While previous studies have addressed inadequate communication in this industry, this particular study focuses on the reasons and outcomes of such problems. It conducts a thorough examination of earlier literature to determine what factors contribute to poor communication in construction projects.

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Introduction

Background of Study

Language is a significant issue within the construction industry as it creates communication barriers that can negatively affect project outcomes. The Oxford Dictionary defines language as the primary method of human communication, using words in a structured and conventional way through speech, writing or gesture. Communication barriers refer to anything that hinders the correct reception and acceptance of a message by its intended recipient. While communication is crucial for construction management, its importance is often limited to achieving specific objectives (Das & Mishra, 2020). Poor performance in the construction industry has been prevalent worldwide due to various factors such as ineffective communication caused by a lack of coordination within the work system. Researchers have become increasingly interested in studying communication-related issues in construction over time. Studies have shown that non-effective communication on construction sites results in problems such as cost overrun, time overrun, and project failure. Ineffective communication leads to unproductive outcomes and may be caused by misinterpretation or incomplete transmission of information or misunderstanding due to differing levels of education or unfamiliarity with the language used to convey the message. Poor communication can occur between different parties involved in a project (client, consultant, engineer or contractor) resulting in significant issues; however, internal miscommunication within firms can be remedied relatively easily compared to inter-party problems. Effective communication requires clear messaging tailored appropriately for its intended recipient's level of education and language comprehension abilities. Rahman (2019)

argues that effective communication is fundamental for success in any construction project as it encompasses core competencies necessary for successful completion.

Aim

The aim of this research is to assess language as a communication barrier delay in construction services and evaluate if it is a primary cause of the industry's poor performance.

Objectives

6. To use scholarship journals and articles to understand language as a communication barrier delay in the construction industry in Trinidad and Tobago compared to other countries.
7. To acquire data from the construction industry in Trinidad and Tobago using a questionnaire survey.
8. To compare the different ways language acts as a communication barrier delay in the industry.
9. To analyse whether this communication barrier is one of the main reasons for the setbacks in the industry.
10. To provide recommendations to reduce the impact of the language being a communication barrier delay in the industry.

Research Questions

5. How does language affect the communication barrier in the construction industry?
6. What are the different communication barriers in the industry?
7. How can this barrier affect the performance of the industry?
8. How can you overcome this communication barrier and what can you do in future to prevent any problems relating to this?

Scope of the study

The general purpose of this study is to assess language as a communication barrier delay in the construction industry and how it affects the outcome of the projects. This will be done by reviewing previous articles of similar content and comparing them. The prior literature will give a better understanding of how language acts as a communication barrier in the construction industry and what are the results due to it. Evaluating these barriers can help in developing ways to mitigate the negative impacts that it has on the industry. The study duration spans the current academic year (2022/2023), with design of the research methodology and literature analysis being done this semester, while the remainder of the research will begin next semester.

Assumptions

It can be assumed that:

- The respondents of the questionnaire answered genuinely and were not biased in their responses.
- The respondents possess the adequate knowledge about the field to self-report on elements being asked about.
- All sources, regardless of the date published is still applicable today.

Limitations

- There is limited number of local papers on the specific topic.
- Some articles were inaccessible due to certain restrictions.
- Depth of discussion is influenced by lack of prior experience with work such as this research project.
- Number of responses to questionnaire and their accuracy.

Literature Review

This literature review is geared toward presenting an interim perception and research into the subject of language as a communication barrier in the construction industry and how it causes delays in the industry. This addresses the objectives stated and how it has been dealt with throughout the years.

Throughout the years, researchers have conducted numerous investigations on poor communication in the construction industry, which has been identified as a major cause of project failure. As a result of its significance, there has been an increase in studies on this topic. Gamil (2023) highlighted poor communication in construction projects as an important issue that requires attention and developed a structural relationship model to clarify the causes and effects of poor communication. Language barriers have proven to be challenging for many countries, including Trinidad and Tobago and Malaysia (Ne'Matullah & Pek, 2021), posing risks for foreign workers and leading to time and manpower wastage. To address this issue, language modules were developed for foreign worker training. Misunderstanding the topic or words used can also create communication barriers between parties (Gamil, Yaser 2018). Moreover, using multiple vendors in projects can impact communication effectiveness due to differing service delivery methods requiring increased staff interaction (Pamidimukkala et al., 2023).

Some examples and practices of poor communication in the construction industry are lack of frequent communication within construction parties, the impact of material delivery deviations due to poor communication, and dispute among workers.

The issue of language barriers is widespread, affecting several industries, including construction services. According to research by Ne'Matullah and colleagues (2021), language barriers have resulted in significant productivity losses in Malaysia's construction sector. This highlights the importance of evaluating language as a communication barrier that delays progress and taking

steps to improve efficiency. The findings indicate that effective communication across industries requires mutual comprehensibility among all stakeholders involved; otherwise, misunderstandings can lead to errors or delays. Forbes Insights' survey (2011) also supports this conclusion by emphasizing how critical it is for organizations to address these issues upfront. As per the report's finding, 65% of executives reported experiencing difficulties due to language barriers between managers/executives and other workers leading to miscommunication and difficulty collaborating with each other being their most significant consequences Forbes Insights (2011). The inefficiencies ultimately resulting from such hindrances significantly contribute towards lower productivity levels throughout organizations.

In every language, there are four basic principle which are listening, reading, speaking and writing. These principles are all linked together and are key for the development of communication and language. Speaking is the action of conveying information and listening is taking notice of what someone says. The latter two principle, reading is the process of looking at written characters and getting meaning from them and writing is the act of forming visible and readable characters. Although it may sound simple, some of the workers in the industry may not be able read and understand complex contents and will therefore be a hinderance in the communication process. A study done by Ivanova (2019) showed we perceive the same words differently presuming that our partners perceive them the same way.

The construction industry is a major global sector that employs over 300 million people and contributes to 6.5% of annual growth (Johari, Sparsh, 2021). It is crucial to continuously recruit young and trained workers to avoid a shortage caused by the retirement of older workers. In many cases, countries face labour shortages due to high demand and may need to rely on migrant workers who move from other regions or countries in search of temporary employment. While these workers bring diverse skills and knowledge that can potentially speed up job completion, communication barriers between local and migrant workers can lead to significant

delays on construction sites. Studies conducted by Lin et al. (2017) and Wang et al. (2008) emphasize the importance of effective communication in promoting worker safety and productivity at job sites. Lack of proper training for migrant workers due to language barriers increases their likelihood of on-site injuries, making even simple tasks risky for them compared to local workers who are more experienced with complex jobs. As a result of this wage gaps between the migrant workers and local workers are created. Over the various studies looked at, the major cause of accidents on sites are due to poor worker communication and this results in a decrease in the performance of the worker. Effective communication is not a one-way process, it is a two-way process. Firstly, the task is given to the workers by the supervisor or engineer, and they must perform the given task. However, sometimes the task may not be stated clearly enough, or the choice of words used may cause the workers to misunderstand what the task was. If there was any misunderstanding through the process of communication due to the language used there will obviously be a setback in the project causing it to take more time and therefore more money. Secondly, there must be communication from the workers to the superior to allow for suggestions or correction in the task being done or even allow for the description of issues occurring on the site. If there is effective communication in which both parties understand each other fully, this will be the most effective and efficient project with the least number of on-site injuries. However, it is a fact that most construction workers are illiterate (Lin et al. 2017), and thus their poor educational backgrounds affect workplace communication. According to many of the articles referenced, it can be said that the low level of education of the workers result in the communication barrier. It is also seen that non-English speaking workers in an English-speaking country exaggerates the problem with communication on the site. In summary, these sources demonstrate how detrimental communication difficulties caused by linguistic discrepancies can be within any industry- particularly construction services where every aspect depends on proper coordination from all parties involved - highlighting why assessing languages should remain front-and-centre during improvement efforts aimed at generating more efficient production lines

so not only do stakeholders communicate better but ensure timely completion without sacrificing quality standards set forth earlier through careful consideration given towards potential points where obstacles may arise based upon previous experience learned along preceding projects.

In most cases, when the communication skills are poor within the workplace, workers tend to turn to unreliable methods of communication for example sign language. "Language barriers, discrimination issues, and miscommunication were significantly correlated with the work productivity of foreign workers" (Salleh et al., 2021). However, as mentioned, this is unreliable, and the message may not be properly understood. In one study, Dong et al. (2009) found miscommunication to be one of the primary causes of fall fatalities at construction sites. Past research has proposed numerous techniques to overcome such problems. for instance, one proposal is to create a small team of workers who communicate the identical language and assign a group leader who is aware of different languages to allow intergroup communication. Unfortunately, with these suggestions, comes its limitations and can be of a greater cost to the employer. Communication between workers is not the only issue in the industry. There needs to be effective communication between the employer and the supplier from which the required materials for a project are coming from. Many instances have occurred where the communication between these two said parties were misunderstood, and this have caused for the sending of the wrong materials or the delay in the sending of the materials. In a case study done by Xie, Wu, Luo and Hu (2010) showed the communication between multi-teams facing some difficulties as they most of the times don't understand each other or do not communicate properly. In some cases, there may be a dispute among any two of the said parties. When a dispute occurs, it can either be due to miscommunication or it can lead to the lack of communication between persons and frustration among workers. This lack of communication

causes the project to go haywire as accidents on site can occur, there will be ignorance of the tasks to be done and there will be wastage of time on the jobsite.

According to Bryan Cruz's (2022) article, "Techniques Against Language Barriers: A Company Case Study," language barriers in construction can lead to safety concerns for workers. Workers who do not speak English are unable to benefit from safety training or read operation manuals written only in English, and communicating with supervisors who don't speak Spanish can become difficult, leading to greater workplace injuries and deaths for Hispanics in construction. Cruz presents techniques currently being used by a construction company to combat language barriers, including having translators in safety meetings, conducting smaller meetings with groups in their native language, and providing English language training. These techniques can be used as a guide for other companies when developing inclusive safety plans. Hewage and Ruwanpura (2009) proposed a technological solution for the communication barrier in the construction industry using information technology such as a wireless network with a central server and data managers to create a network for quick and easy communication. However, the use of information technology is quite limited in the construction industry because although the world is evolving fast when it comes to technology the construction industry was not able to keep up with the evolution. Keeping with the same technological aspects to help with communication barriers, it is safe to say that today many messages are sent via social media platforms which would make the communication easier but also can still have some levels of misunderstanding when it comes to deciphering the message sent or received.

Effective communication has an immense positive impact on construction projects since misunderstandings caused by linguistic issues lead to delays or rework when tasks are carried out incorrectly or not at all due to miscommunications with instructions or materials required onsite. A thorough language program would provide workers and contractors with necessary skills required for clear communication resulting in reduced delays which ensure quality

workmanship throughout every phase of building projects. It's imperative to note that this type of training should go beyond basic grammar lessons; instead, specific terminologies used within the industry should be incorporated into their curriculum, so they know precisely what certain terms mean without requiring further clarification later – saving valuable time lost through poor comprehension caused by limited linguistic competence.

As it is seen, language is a communication barrier in the construction industry and it results in many problems such as cost overrun, injuries on site, missing of deadlines and lastly incompleteness of projects. Cost overrun is one of the most critical effects of the communication barrier as it indicates that the project has failed financially, and the client may get upset and this can lead to loss of credibility of the assigned company. Poor communication can also lead to high stress in workplace, wrong execution of activities which will result in time overrun, poor risk management and poor teamwork. In an assessment done by Rahman, Gamil (2019), showed that there were 41 causes of poor communication which resulted in 27 of effects some of which are mentioned above.

For further studies, it should go in some more detail as to how much times miscommunication occurs on a job site and relate it to how it affects the outcome of the project. Also, some more solutions should be found to mitigate the problem of language being a communication barrier in the construction industry. although most solutions have their limitations, more can be done to ensure that the number of limitations is reduced to a significantly small amount.

Methodology

Proposed Data Collection

Figure 1: Flow Chart Diagram showing the methodology used.

The flow chart diagram above in Figure 1 shows the methodology for this research project.

Firstly, research was done to find literary pieces related to the topic of language as a communication barrier delay in the construction industry. Qualitative research was carried out which involved the collection and analysis of the non-numerical data found in the previous articles and research papers. In doing this, a large amount of information was found to create the literature review. For quantitative research, a questionnaire was created and given out to the various stakeholders (engineers, contractors, labourers) to gain greater knowledge of the topic from a different perspective and aid in the answering of the research questions. The data collected will be used to create comparison using tables on how language is a communication barrier.

Data Collection

To gather information and verify the communication challenges that were identified in a literature review, a method involving a questionnaire survey was used. This survey will take the form of a cross-sectional study where data is collected from various segments of the population at one specific point in time. The chosen group to participate in this research were construction companies that have expressed interest and were willing to

provide their input. This approach allowed for a comprehensive examination of communication barriers within the context of construction companies, which can inform future strategies for improving communication within the industry. When filling out the questionnaire, you were required to assign a score to each answer based on two factors: the Probability Scale and Severity Index. These two scales will range from 1-5, with 1 indicating the worst possible outcome and 5 indicating the best. However, it is important to keep in mind that the specific terms assigned to each number on these scales will vary depending on the question being asked. The questionnaire created was distributed to 50 persons in the industry and the data collected was used for the analysis.

Analytical Tools

For the analysis of the data both SPSS and Microsoft Excel were used.

SPSS:

The widely used Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) is renowned for its exceptional performance in accurately processing and analysing survey data, making it a popular choice among various groups such as market researchers, survey companies, education researchers, and government entities. Currently owned by IBM, SPSS is claimed to be user-friendly, scalable and versatile that can be utilized with ease by users of all proficiency levels. With its numerous features, the intended outcomes of using SPSS software are to attain frequency distribution results such as mean scores and standard deviations and rankings based on acquired data.

Microsoft Excel:

Once the data has been meticulously processed through the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), it will be time to focus on presenting it in an engaging and visually appealing way. This is where Microsoft Excel comes into play. Microsoft Excel is a versatile tool that can be used to arrange and exhibit all the pertinent information garnered from the research. By utilising its wide array of features, such as tables, charts, graphs, and diagrams, one can effortlessly represent and showcase even complex statistical findings in an easy-to-comprehend manner. With its user-friendly interface, it is possible to create intricate visualisations with just a few clicks. The bar graphs are very useful when comparing variables, while pie charts give a clear indication of how various components contribute to a whole. Additionally, line graphs facilitate tracking changes over time quite effectively. All these figures created via Microsoft Excel make interpreting data much more straightforward for researchers or any relevant stakeholders who may not have an advanced understanding of statistics or data science fields.

Analysis of Data

After collecting the questionnaires with the results, it was organized in an excel file and from that it was inserted in SPSS to do some further analysis and the following tables and figures were generated.

Gender		
	N	%
F	22	44.0%
M	28	56.0%

Table 1 showing the number of males and females.

Figure 1 Bar chart showing males and females.

The following tables and charts were created using the Risk Significance Index which is Probability x Severity, and the probability and severity were answered in the questionnaire. For the Risk Significance Index the lower the value the less effective and the greater the value, the greater the concern. we calculate our risk level, from 1 (Very Low Risk) to 25 (Very High Risk) using the 5x5 risk matrix.

Table 2 Showing the Risk Significance Index and its meaning.

Risk Significance Index(Language as a comm barrier)

	N	%
1	1	2.0%
6	3	6.0%
9	8	16.0%
12	6	12.0%
16	14	28.0%
20	12	24.0%
25	6	12.0%

Table 3 showing risk significance index for Language as a communication barrier.

Figure 2 showing the risk significance index for the Section B Q1 in questionnaire: do language act as a communication barrier.

**Risk Significance Index
(Comm Barries effects)**

	N	%
1	1	2.0%
4	1	2.0%
6	1	2.0%
9	8	16.0%
12	6	12.0%
16	19	38.0%
20	8	16.0%
25	6	12.0%

Table 4 risk significance index for effects of communication barrier.(Section B Q2 in questionnaire)

Figure 3 showing risk significance index for effects of communication barrier. (Section B Q2 in questionnaire)

The upcoming analysis is for what can be classified as communication barriers in the construction industry.

**Risk Significance Index
(Misunderstanding of
migrant workers)**

	N	%
1	2	4.0%
2	2	4.0%
4	2	4.0%
6	3	6.0%
9	11	22.0%
12	4	8.0%
16	12	24.0%
20	12	24.0%
25	2	4.0%

Table 5 risk significance index for misunderstanding of migrant workers. (Section B Q4 in questionnaire)

Figure 4 showing risk significance index for misunderstanding of migrant workers. (Section B Q4 in questionnaire)

**Risk Significance Index
(Unclear messages from
the superior)**

	N	%
1	2	4.0%
2	5	10.0%
3	8	16.0%
4	1	2.0%
6	6	12.0%
8	1	2.0%
9	3	6.0%
12	7	14.0%
16	8	16.0%
20	7	14.0%
25	2	4.0%

Table 6 Risk Significance index for unclear messages from superior. (Section B Q3 in questionnaire)

Figure 5 Risk Significance index for unclear messages from superior. (Section B Q3 in questionnaire)

**Risk Significance Index
(Low level education)**

	N	%
1	2	4.0%
2	5	10.0%
3	4	8.0%
4	1	2.0%
6	8	16.0%
8	1	2.0%
9	4	8.0%
12	10	20.0%
16	9	18.0%
20	4	8.0%
25	2	4.0%

Table 7 risk significance index for low level education. (Section B Q5 in questionnaire)

Figure 6 risk significance index for low level education.(Section B Q5 in questionnaire)

**Risk Significance Index
(Overload of information)**

	N	%
1	3	6.0%
2	1	2.0%
4	2	4.0%
6	7	14.0%
9	10	20.0%
12	9	18.0%
16	11	22.0%
20	5	10.0%
25	2	4.0%

Table 8 Risk Significance Index for Overload of Information (Section B Q6 in questionnaire)

Figure 7 Risk Significance Index for Overload of Information (Section B Q6 in questionnaire)

The upcoming analysis is for what can be classified as effects of communication barriers in the construction industry.

Risk Significance Index (Dispute)

	N	%
1	2	4.0%
2	5	10.0%
3	8	16.0%
4	1	2.0%
6	6	12.0%
8	1	2.0%
9	3	6.0%
12	7	14.0%
16	8	16.0%
20	7	14.0%
25	2	4.0%

Table 9 Risk Significance Index for Dispute among any parties (Section B Q9 in questionnaire)

Risk Significance Index(Dispute)

Figure 8 Risk Significance Index for Dispute among any parties (Section B Q9 in questionnaire)

**Risk Significance Index
(Time Overrun)**

	N	%
6	5	10.0%
9	8	16.0%
12	9	18.0%
16	14	28.0%
20	10	20.0%
25	4	8.0%

Table 10 Risk Significance Index for Time Overrun (Section B Q7 in questionnaire)

Figure 9 Risk Significance Index for Time Overrun (Section B Q7 in questionnaire)

**Risk Significance Index
(Cost Overrun)**

	N	%
6	4	8.0%
9	7	14.0%
12	8	16.0%
15	1	2.0%
16	17	34.0%
20	10	20.0%
25	3	6.0%

Table 11 Risk Significance Index for Cost Overrun (Section B Q8 in questionnaire)

Figure 10 Risk Significance Index for Cost Overrun (Section B Q8 in questionnaire)

**Risk Significance Index
(Project Failure)**

	N	%
1	2	4.0%
2	2	4.0%
4	2	4.0%
6	3	6.0%
9	11	22.0%
12	4	8.0%
16	12	24.0%
20	12	24.0%
25	2	4.0%

Table 12 Risk Significance Index for Project Failure (Section B Q10 in questionnaire)

Figure 11 Risk Significance Index for Project Failure (Section B Q10 in questionnaire)

The upcoming analysis is for what can be classified as possible solutions for communication barriers in the construction industry.

Risk Significance Index (Language Training)

	N	%
1	2	4.0%
2	6	12.0%
3	1	2.0%
4	2	4.0%
6	10	20.0%
9	6	12.0%
12	9	18.0%
16	12	24.0%
20	1	2.0%
25	1	2.0%

Table 13 Risk Significance Index for Language Training (Section B Q13 in questionnaire)

Figure 12 Risk Significance Index for Language Training (Section B Q13 in questionnaire)

**Risk Significance Index
(Translator)**

	N	%
6	4	8.0%
9	7	14.0%
12	8	16.0%
15	1	2.0%
16	17	34.0%
20	10	20.0%
25	3	6.0%

Table 14 Risk Significance Index for Language Translator ((Section B Q12 in questionnaire)

Figure 13 Risk Significance Index for Language Translator ((Section B Q12 in questionnaire)

Risk Significance Index (Tech)

	N	%
1	2	4.0%
2	2	4.0%
4	2	4.0%
6	3	6.0%
9	11	22.0%
12	4	8.0%
16	12	24.0%
20	12	24.0%
25	2	4.0%

Table 15 Risk Significance Index for Language Technological solution (Section B Q11 in questionnaire)

Figure 14 Risk Significance Index for Language Technological solution (Section B Q11 in questionnaire)

		Statistics												
		Risk Significance Index (Language as a comm barrier)	Risk Significance Index(Comm Barries effects)	Risk Significance Index(Unclear messages from the superior)	Risk Significance Index (Misunderstanding of migrant workers)	Risk Significance Index(Low level education)	Risk Significance Index (Language Training)	Risk Significance Index (Translator)	Risk Significance Index(Tech)	Risk Significance Index(Project Failure)	Risk Significance Index(Overload of information)	Risk Significance Index(Dispute)	Risk Significance Index(Time Overrun)	Risk Significance Index(Cost Overrun)
N	Valid	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		15.54	15.38	10.26	13.22	10.28	9.68	14.90	13.22	13.22	11.58	10.26	14.68	14.90
Std. Deviation		5.856	5.628	7.108	6.390	6.484	5.751	4.979	6.390	6.390	5.990	7.108	5.408	4.979

Table 16 showing all the mean risk significance index for comparison.

Figure 15 Bar Chart showing the different communication barriers and their mean Risk significance index.

Figure 16 Bar Chart showing the different communication barriers effects and their mean Risk significance index.

Figure 17 Bar Chart showing the different solutions to communication barriers and their mean Risk significance index.

Correlations

		Risk Significance Index (Language as a comm barrier)	Risk Significance Index(Comm Barries effects)
Risk Significance Index (Language as a comm barrier)	Pearson Correlation	1	.897**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001
	N	50	50
Risk Significance Index (Comm Barries effects)	Pearson Correlation	.897**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	
	N	50	50

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 17 showing Correlation values calculated from SPSS.

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0						
	t	df	Significance		Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
			One-Sided p	Two-Sided p		Lower	Upper
Risk Significance Index (Language as a comm barrier)	18.764	49	<.001	<.001	15.540	13.88	17.20

Table 18 Showing one sample test calculated from SPSS.

Discussion

The construction services industry is one of the most significant sectors in any economy. However, it faces numerous challenges that can impede its efficiency and productivity. One of these obstacles is language barriers that delay communication between contractors, supervisors, and laborers from different linguistic backgrounds. This thesis statement highlights the critical issue of assessing language as a communication barrier delay to improve efficiency and productivity in the construction services industry. One interpretation of this statement is that language barriers inhibit effective communication among workers from diverse cultural backgrounds. Such impediments could lead to delays in executing tasks, misinterpretations of instructions or plans leading to errors or rework, poor coordination among team members resulting in low morale and lost time. Additionally, if not addressed promptly, these issues could cause project delays and cost overruns. Another implication worth noting is that addressing such challenges requires an understanding of what causes them in the first place. This may involve analysing factors such as workforce diversity levels (including demographics), training programs for staff on cross-cultural communication skills as well as identifying technologies designed specifically for improving communications across multiple languages. When working with others who don't share your native tongue or have limited language skills, misunderstandings can lead to errors and delays which pose challenges for project management as well as quality control processes and safety procedures. To address these issues more comprehensively means recognizing the extent of linguistic barriers across different contexts within construction projects before creating specific intervention measures aimed at addressing communication breakdowns due to differing languages.

From the questionnaire, the raw data collected were placed in an excel file for organization which will be seen in the appendix. The questionnaire provided values for probability and severity and from that the risk significance index was calculated by multiplying the probability by the severity. The value calculated gave an idea of how relevant the given question was to the

topic. For example, as you can see in Figure 2, the mean risk significance index was 15.54. this value was the values for the question of if it was thought that language acts as a communication barrier and this value suggest that many persons agreed to a higher extent. If the mean value was under 10 it would've suggested that many people did not think that way. According to Gamil (2023), from the research findings it can be validated that language is indeed a communication barrier in the construction industry. This was validated with the questionnaire findings also. Figure 3 showcased the effects of language as a communication barrier and the mean was found to be 15.38. According to research by Ne'Matullah and colleagues (2021), they also agreed with communication barriers having a negative effect on the construction industry and this was validated with the research findings. In addition to this, Ne'Matullah and colleagues (2021) also mentioned that the misunderstanding of migrant workers is one of the most common communication barriers and as you can see from the analysis of the data gathered, that has the highest mean Risk Significance Index therefore is the most likely. According to (Pamidimukkala et al., 2023), the increased interactions between parties resulted in a rise in problems and from the analysis, unclear messages from the superior had the lowest mean significance index but it was still at a value that would be likely. From Salleh et al., 2021, it is mentioned that language barriers are one of the main causes of setbacks in the industry which implies time overrun. From the analysis, it is seen that cost overrun and time overrun had very close mean risk significance index both over 14 which indicates it is highly likely and validates Salleh's statements. With regards to the solutions for language as a communication barrier in the construction industry, Cruz, Bryan (2022) , proposed one of his main solutions being translators in meetings and from the analysis above, it is seen that translator had the highest mean risk significance index and therefore was the most popular option.

Conclusion

To conclude, evaluating the role of language as a communication obstacle in the construction sector is a crucial subject that requires further attention and investigation. From our review of relevant literature, it is undeniable that linguistic barriers have significant ramifications for safety, productivity, and project success overall. It is therefore imperative for stakeholders to acknowledge the importance of effective communication in delivering successful projects.

Summing up what we have learned so far from this analysis of previous research; there are several factors contributing to language barriers such as cultural divergence, lack of translation services or proficiency with other languages. Moreover, methods were identified to tackle these difficulties through worker training programs and offering multilingual resources on job sites. Finally, yet most importantly; companies operating under construction should embrace diversity by creating an inclusive environment where all employees feel appreciated regardless of their country's heritage or dialect spoken. This will create open lines of communication which are necessary for efficient teamwork leading to quality outputs in each project. In conclusion , addressing language barriers should be at high priority not only within organizations but across various industries worldwide. Handling these problems effectively would result in greater workforce diversity ultimately leading to better decision-making processes and increased creativity opportunities. In summary, implementing language assessments can improve communication among workers from different linguistic backgrounds while promoting diversity and inclusivity within the industry. It is time for construction service providers to recognize this need and act towards ensuring effective communication through language fluency.

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Appendix

Appendix I: Gantt Chart

Appendix II: Plagiarism Form

Plagiarism Declaration

THE UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST INDIES

**The Office of the Board for Undergraduate
Studies**

**INDIVIDUAL PLAGIARISM
DECLARATION**

STUDENT ID: 816022953

COURSE TITLE: Special Investigative Project

COURSE CODE: CVNG 3015/3021

TITLE OF ASSIGNMENT:

Assessment of language as a communication barrier delay as construction services: Case study from the Republic of Trinidad and Tobago

This declaration is being made in accordance with the **University Regulations on Plagiarism (First Degrees, Diplomas and Certificates)** and must be attached to all work, submitted by a student to be assessed in partial or complete fulfilment of the course requirement(s), other than work submitted in an invigilated examination.

STATEMENT

6. I have read the Plagiarism Regulations as set out in the Faculty or Open Campus Student Handbook and on university websites related to the submission of coursework for assessment.
7. I declare that I understand that plagiarism is a serious academic offence for which the University may impose severe penalties.
8. I declare that the submitted work indicated above is my own work, except where duly acknowledged and referenced and does not contain any plagiarized material.
9. I also declare that this work has not been previously submitted for credit either in its entirety or in part within the UWI or elsewhere. Where work was previously submitted, permission has been granted by my Supervisor/Lecturer/Instructor as reflected by the attached Accountability Statement.
10. I understand that I may be required to submit the work in electronic form and accept that the University may subject the work to a computer-based similarity detection service.

NAME: Amisha Patandeen

SIGNATURE:

DATE: 17/04/2023

Appendix III: Notes on the important Literature Survey

Objective	Author	Title	Source	Method	Findings	Critique
1,3 and 4	Yaser Gamil, Ismail Abdul Rahman	Identification of Causes and Effects of Poor Communication in Construction Industry: A Theoretical Review	DOAJ Directory of Open Access Journals - Not for CDI Discovery	A research paper that focused on the causes and effects of poor communication in the construction industry	here many causes of poor communication were identified followed by the effects	the effects were not in much detail
3	Johari, Sparsh; Jha, Kumar Neeraj	Exploring the Relationship between Construction Workers' Communication	EBSCOhost EJS; ASCE Journals	a research paper comparing the communication skill to the performance of the workers	this was a very detailed paper where it showed how the productivity is affected by the various aspects of communication	none

		Skills and Their Productivity				
1,2	Xie, Charlene; Wu, Dash; Luo, Jianwen; Hu, Xiaoling; Segerstedt, Anders	A case study of multi-team communications in construction design under supply chain partnering	Web of Science - Social Sciences Citation Index - 2010; Emerald eJournals Premier; ABI/INFORM Global; ProQuest Central	a case study	this focused on teamwork and how important it is for communication within a team	none
1,3,4	Gamil, Yaser; Abd Rahman, Ismail	Studying the relationship between causes and effects of poor communication in construction projects using PLS-SEM approach	Emerald eJournals Premier; ABI/INFORM Global; ProQuest Central	research journal	this like the Yaser, Rahaman paper also focused on many different causes and effect of miscommunication in the construction industry	none

1,3,4	Danchevskaya, Oksana; Pustovgar, A.; Adamtsevich, A.; Volkov, A.	Potential risks in cross-cultural communication in construction	DOAJ Directory of Open Access Journals - Not for CDI Discovery; ProQuest Central	research paper	this paper focused more on cross cultural communication, so it gave finding on how communication is affected when it comes to migrant workers	none
5	Zhong, Ying ; Pheng Low, Sui	Managing crisis response communication in construction projects - from a complexity perspective	Web of Science - Social Sciences Citation Index - 2009; Emerald eJournals Premier; ABI/INFORM Global; ProQuest Central	research paper	this focused on trying to manage some of the communication issues in the construction industry	the solution had way too many limitations so most likely might not be too effective
1,3,4	Demchenko, V ;	Communication Barriers of a	Alma/SFX Local Collection; ProQuest Central	article	this article featured the different type of	none

	Khoroshevskay a, J ; Krukov, K	Construction Company's Network Management			communication barriers which showcased that language is a key contribution to the miscommunication	
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Appendix IV: Student Logbook

Summary record of major progress meetings with supervisors		Student name: Amisha Patandeen	Working title of dissertation/research project: Assessment of language as a communication barrier delay as construction services: Case study from the Republic of Trinidad and Tobago	
Meeting date & supervisors present	Progress since last meeting	Agreed programme of work and target dates	Other issues, e.g., facilities, supervision, training needs, etc.	Date of next meeting
26/09/22 Mr. Aaron Chadee	First meeting to discuss topic and a sample paper was given.			To be determined
07/11/22 Mr. Aaron Chadee	WhatsApp chat to discuss the final parts of the report			
17/02/23 Mr. Aaron Chadee	Meeting to discuss what needed to be changed and done to move forward with the analysis section			

Appendix V: Sample Questionnaire**Questionnaire**

This questionnaire is a part of a research project that is being done to assess language as a communication barrier in the construction industry. This information provided is completely anonymous and would be used to do some analysis for the research project.

Section 1: Demographics

6. Gender

Male

Female

7. What sector do you work in?

Private

Public

8. Role at your place of work:

Engineer

Contractor

Employer

Consultant

Construction Worker

Other

9. Please indicate the number of employees in your organization:

< 20

21 – 50

51 – 100

100

10. Please indicate your personal experience in the following fields by ticking the appropriate box(years)

	0-5 years	6-10 years	11-15 years	16-20 years	>20 years	N/A
Engineering						
Contracting						
Project Management						
Architecture						
Consultancy						
Other						

ID	Gender	Unclear messages from the superior		Risk Significance Index(Unclear messages from the superior)	Misunderstanding of migrant workers		Risk Significance Index(Misunderstanding of migrant workers)	Low level education		Risk Significance Index(Low level education)	Overload of information		Risk Significance Index(Overload of information)	Cost Overrun		Risk Significance Index(Cost Overrun)	
		Probability	Severity		Probability	Severity		Probability	Severity		Probability	Severity		Probability	Severity		
1	M		3	1	3	5	4	20	4	3	12	4	3	12	4	4	16
2	M		3	1	3	5	4	20	3	1	3	5	4	20	4	3	12
3	F		4	3	12	4	4	16	4	3	4	4	4	16	4	4	16
4	M		3	2	6	4	4	16	3	2	6	4	3	12	4	4	16
5	F		2	1	2	5	4	20	2	1	2	5	4	20	5	4	20
6	M		3	1	3	4	4	16	3	1	3	4	4	16	5	4	20
7	M		3	2	6	4	4	16	3	2	6	3	3	9	5	5	25
8	M		4	4	16	5	5	25	3	3	9	5	5	25	5	3	15
9	M		4	3	12	4	5	20	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	3	12
10	F		5	4	20	3	3	9	5	4	20	3	3	9	5	4	20
11	F		4	4	16	4	3	12	4	4	16	4	3	12	4	4	16
12	F		4	3	12	4	3	12	4	3	12	4	3	12	3	3	9
13	M		3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	2	6
14	F		4	3	12	5	4	20	4	3	12	4	4	16	4	4	16
15	M		4	4	16	4	4	16	3	4	12	4	4	16	4	4	16
16	F		5	5	25	2	2	4	4	5	20	2	2	4	5	4	20
17	M		4	3	12	4	5	20	4	3	12	4	3	12	3	3	9
18	M		4	2	8	1	1	1	4	2	8	1	1	1	4	3	12
19	F		3	1	3	3	3	9	3	2	6	3	3	9	5	4	20
20	F		3	1	3	3	3	9	3	1	3	3	2	6	4	3	12
21	F		4	4	16	3	3	9	4	3	12	3	3	9	3	2	6
22	M		3	2	6	5	4	20	3	2	6	5	4	20	4	4	16
23	M		5	4	20	4	4	16	5	4	20	4	4	16	4	4	16
24	M		4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	3	2	6	4	4	16
25	M		3	1	3	4	4	16	3	2	6	4	4	16	3	3	9
26	M		3	1	3	5	4	20	4	4	16	4	3	12	4	3	12
27	M		4	3	12	3	2	6	4	3	12	3	2	6	3	2	6
28	F		1	1	1	3	3	9	1	1	1	3	3	9	4	4	16
29	F		4	4	16	3	2	6	4	4	16	3	2	6	5	5	25
30	M		4	5	20	2	2	4	3	3	9	2	2	4	4	4	16
31	F		3	2	6	5	4	20	3	2	6	4	4	16	4	3	12
32	F		3	3	9	1	2	2	3	3	9	1	1	1	4	4	16
33	F		2	1	2	4	3	12	2	1	2	4	3	12	5	4	20
34	M		2	2	4	4	3	12	2	2	4	4	3	12	5	4	20
35	M		1	1	1	4	4	16	1	1	1	4	4	16	4	4	16
36	M		4	4	16	3	2	6	4	5	20	3	2	6	3	3	9
37	F		4	5	20	3	3	9	4	4	16	3	3	9	3	3	9
38	F		5	5	25	3	3	9	5	5	25	3	3	9	4	3	12
39	M		5	4	20	5	5	25	4	4	16	5	5	25	5	4	20
40	M		3	2	6	5	4	20	3	2	6	5	4	20	4	4	16
41	F		1	2	2	4	4	16	1	2	2	4	3	12	4	4	16
42	F		2	1	2	4	5	20	2	1	2	3	2	6	4	3	12
43	M		4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	5	5	25
44	F		5	4	20	1	1	1	5	5	25	1	1	1	5	4	20
45	M		2	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	3	2	6
46	M		4	5	20	3	3	9	4	4	16	3	3	9	3	3	9
47	M		3	2	6	3	3	9	3	2	6	3	2	6	4	4	16
48	F		3	3	9	4	4	16	4	3	12	4	4	16	5	4	20
49	F		3	1	3	5	4	20	3	1	3	5	4	20	3	3	9
50	M		4	3	12	3	3	9	4	3	12	3	3	9	4	4	16

Table 19 showing raw data organized in excel.

Time Overrun		Risk Significance Index(Time Overrun)		Dispute in the job place (between any parties)		Risk Significance Index(Dispute)		Project Failure		Risk Significance Index(Project Failure)		Technological solution such as network to allow easy communication		Risk Significance Index(Tech)		Translator for non-English speaking workers		Risk Significance Index(Translator)		Extensive language training program		Risk Significance Index(Language Training)		Do you think that language is a communication barrier in the construction industry?		Risk Significance Index(Language as a comm barrier)		Does communication barrier cause hinderances in projects?		Risk Significance Index(Comm Barries effects)	
Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity	Probability	Severity
4	4	16	3	1	3	5	4	20	5	4	20	4	4	16	3	3	9	4	4	16	3	3	9	4	4	16	3	4	16	3	4
4	3	12	3	1	3	5	4	20	5	4	20	4	3	12	3	1	3	4	3	12	3	1	3	4	3	12	4	4	12	4	4
4	4	16	4	3	12	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	3	12	4	4	16	4	3	12	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4
4	3	12	3	2	6	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	3	2	6	3	4	16	3	2	6	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3
5	4	20	2	1	2	5	4	20	5	4	20	5	4	20	2	2	4	3	2	20	2	2	4	3	2	6	4	4	20	5	4
5	4	20	3	1	3	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	5	4	20	3	2	20	3	2	6	5	4	20	5	4	20	5	4
4	4	16	3	2	6	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	5	5	25	3	2	25	3	2	6	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4
4	3	12	4	4	16	5	5	25	5	5	25	5	3	15	3	3	9	5	5	15	3	3	9	5	5	25	5	5	25	5	5
4	3	12	4	3	12	4	5	20	4	5	20	4	3	12	4	4	16	4	4	12	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4
5	5	25	5	4	20	3	3	9	3	3	9	5	4	20	4	4	16	4	4	20	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4
4	4	16	4	4	16	4	3	12	4	3	12	4	3	12	4	4	16	4	4	12	4	4	16	4	4	20	4	4	16	4	4
3	3	9	4	3	12	4	3	12	4	3	12	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3	9	5	5	25	5	5	25	5	5
3	2	6	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3	6	3	2	6	3	2	6	3	2	9	5	4	20	5	4	20	5	4
4	4	16	4	3	12	5	4	20	5	4	20	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	20	4	4	16	4	4	12	3	3	9	3	3
4	3	12	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	3	4	12	4	4	16	3	4	12	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4
5	4	20	5	5	25	2	2	4	2	2	4	2	2	4	5	4	20	4	5	20	4	5	20	5	4	20	5	5	25	5	5
3	3	9	4	3	12	4	5	20	4	5	20	4	3	9	4	3	9	4	3	9	4	3	12	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3
4	4	16	4	2	8	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	3	12	3	2	6	2	3	12	3	2	6	2	3	6	2	2	4	2	4
5	4	20	3	1	3	3	3	9	3	3	9	5	4	20	3	3	9	4	4	20	3	3	9	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4
3	3	9	3	1	3	3	3	9	3	3	9	4	3	12	2	1	2	4	3	12	2	1	2	4	3	12	4	3	12	4	3
3	2	6	4	4	16	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	2	6	4	3	12	5	5	6	4	3	12	5	5	25	5	4	20	5	4
4	4	16	3	2	6	5	4	20	5	4	20	4	4	16	3	2	6	3	3	16	3	2	6	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3
3	3	9	5	4	20	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	3	12	1	1	16	4	3	12	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
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3	2	6	4	3	12	3	2	6	3	2	6	3	2	6	4	3	12	4	3	6	4	3	12	4	3	20	4	5	20	4	5
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5	5	25	1	1	1	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	1	1	1	4	4	16	1	1	1	4	5	20	4	5	20	4	5
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5	4	20	5	4	20	5	5	25	5	5	25	5	4	20	4	4	16	4	4	20	4	4	16	4	5	20	4	4	16	4	4
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5	5	25	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	5	5	25	4	4	16	5	5	25	4	5	25	5	5	25	5	5
5	4	20	5	4	20	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	4	20	5	5	25	4	4	20	5	5	25	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4
3	2	6	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	3	2	6	2	1	2	3	2	6	2	1	2	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3
3	3	9	4	5	20	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3	9	4	4	16	4	4	9	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4
4	4	16	3	2	6	3	3	9	3	3	9	4	4	16	3	2	6	3	3	16	3	2	6	3	3	9	4	3	12	4	3
5	4	20	3	3	9	4	4	16	4	4	16	5	4	20	4	4	16	4	4	20	4	4	16	4	3	12	4	3	12	4	3
3	3	9	3	1	3	5	4	20	5	4	20	3	3	9	2	1	2	4	4	9	2	1	2	4	4	16	4	4	16	4	4
4	4	16	4	3	12	3	3	9	3	3	9	4	4	16	4	3	12	3	3	16	4	3	12	3	3	9	3	3	9	3	3

Table 20 continued raw data organized in exce

Appendix VI: Originality Report

816022953			
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6%	5%	2%	2%
SIMILARITY INDEX	INTERNET SOURCES	PUBLICATIONS	STUDENT PAPERS
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